

Performance Practice of Electroacoustic Music. Towards a practice-based exchange between musicology and performance

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ABSTRACT

The following is a report on a research project dedicated to problems presented by the performance of electroacoustic music. It was realized between 2014 and 2016 at the Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology of the Zurich University of the Arts. In this paper, the project's structure and methodology, combining musicological and practice-based approaches, is explained and selected issues encountered in studying and performing the repertoire are discussed focusing on specific compositions. Two main research output products are presented. Finally, a brief evaluation of findings is given, as well as an outlook on future performance practice studies at ICST.

1. INTRODUCTION

The repertoire of electroacoustic music, which has been emerging since the second half of the 20th century, has firmly established itself in today's concert programmes. At the same time, problems concerning its performance practice have become increasingly relevant. For electroacoustic performers, in particular, the question of how to present early pieces in concert taking into account their specific artistic, historic and technical genesis becomes critical, considering that the technical means available nowadays are completely different from historical conditions. Many composers who traditionally have been the foremost interpreters of their own music are now at old age or no longer alive. The same can be said of other important witnesses to history such as instrumentalists, conductors, technicians, studio assistants and musicians concerned with performance and sound projection.

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The disappearance of old technologies and the availability of new ones present challenges while opening up new possibilities. Different attitudes and experiences of today's audiences must be taken into account as well.

As in instrumental performance practice of older music, those questions lead into an area marked by the tension between historical performance practice and modern reception. The preservation of knowledge about the genesis of electroacoustic works, the original performance conditions and the development of a performance tradition is an essential prerequisite for developing an adequately informed performance practice. To contribute to its establishment was the overarching goal of the research project discussed in this paper. The practice-based dialogue into which performers and musicologists entered in its course should provide a model for research methodology and yield concrete results with respect to exemplary performance problems posed by the pieces studied.

2. THE RESEARCH PROJECT

The research project *Performance Practice of Electroacoustic Music. Towards a practice-based exchange between musicology and performance*, funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) was realized between September 2014 and August 2016 at ICST/ZHdK¹ in collaboration with the Paul Sacher-Stiftung, Basle. The project team included Germán Toro Pérez (project lead), Florian Bogner and Carlos Hidalgo (performance team), and Lucas Bennett and Federica di Gasbarro (musicology team). A permanent board advising the project team and participating in the workshops included Angela de Benedictis, Pascal Decroupet and Veniero Rizzardi (musicology) and Kilian Schwoon, Kees Tazelaar and Alvise Vidolin (performance). Additional experts were invited to specific workshops. The project was structured in four cycles, each concluding with workshops and concerts open to the public.

Cycle one was dedicated to tape pieces, cycle two to pieces for tape and instruments/voice, cycle three also included pieces with chamber formations. In the fourth and last cycle, pieces with various formats, including large

¹ ICST - Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology / ZHdK - Zurich University of the Arts

settings and multimedia were studied. In preparation of the workshops, the core team would localize and study available sources for a piece including archival material and identify specific performance issues. This was followed by a rehearsal process involving the whole core team and performers. The issues and findings were then presented to the expert panel during workshops and finally, the pieces were presented in public concerts at the end of each workshop. While it is impossible to cover the whole range of problems studied, the following points out some main issues encountered.²

3. SOURCE-RELATED ISSUES

The knowledge of available sources for a piece as well as their historic context is relevant not only for making the best audio source available for performance, it can also be decisive for understanding the formats originally intended for performance. However, such information is often not provided with or reflected by the official performance material distributed by publishers.

For Edgard Varèse's *Poème électronique* (1958), the focus lay on the complicated situation with respect to its sources, the goal ultimately being to better understand the work's original conception. A stereo version of Varèse's music published on record was merely a downmix of the 3-track perfo-tape that had originally been projected over several hundred loudspeakers at the Philips pavilion at the Brussels World Fair of 1958. [1] The performance audio received from the publisher during the project was likewise a 2-channel reduction and proved to be altogether unsuitable for performance, as it was heavily distorted and exhibited a great deal of clipping. Apart from this obvious quality issue, it would seem worthwhile to consider other formats for the performance material than the reduced stereo and to make available for example the original three audio channels or a pre-spatialized surround format. Kees Tazelaar's 5.1 film version (s. 6.) could serve as an example.

As *Poème*, Ligeti's one-channel piece *Glissandi* (1957) raises questions with respect to the quality and provenance of the performance material rented by the publisher on CD. The tape noise was considerable, a powerline hum at 50 Hz, most probably not audible using studio speakers of the time, was present as well as numerous low clicks and dropouts, the latter possibly stemming from an earlier DAT transfer. For this project, some of the audio problems could be corrected digitally. Later, transfers of first-generation copies of the piece made at the WDR (Westdeutscher Rundfunk) and held at the Institute of Sonology, The Hague, were located, which revealed much better audio quality than the performance material. It follows that the original WDR tapes need to be located, inspected and transferred in the best possible way in order for the performance material to reflect the quality of the original material.

Helmut Lachenmann's only tape piece *Szenario*, written in 1965 at IPEM (University of Ghent) has never been officially published, however, several CD releases of varying quality have been available for some time. Through these, the piece was hitherto known as a mono piece, the source presumably being the mono tape held at IPEM that had been used for the original monophonic radio broadcast.³ When looking for the available tape material at IPEM's archive, we found the 4-track master tape of *Szenario*. Contemporary documentation at IPEM⁴ as well as the continuous movement of sounds between the four channels of the 4-channel master tape suggest that *Szenario* was actually conceived as a 4-channel piece. Further investigation of this question would also have to take into account the sketches for the piece.

4. SOUND PROJECTION ISSUES

Written in the year following the composition of *Glissandi*, Ligeti's tape piece *Artikulation* (1958) uses 4 channels. In our experience, the piece has been and is often performed using a rectangular «standard» speaker setup. However, Rainer Wehinger's «Hörpartitur» (listening score), which was first published in 1970 and was described by Ligeti as accurate [2] depicts a disposition according to the cardinal points of the space, forming a rhombus rather than a rectangle. This disposition is also reflected in a sketch for the piece showing the spatial disposition [3]. We don't know if this disposition was observed in earlier performances, however, in later performance practice it seems to have been superseded by the standard rectangular setup, if only for practical reasons. In this project, the rhombus setup was used for performance. For the ensuing SACD release (s. 7.2), however, the rectangular setup was used again, as the central back channel 3 could not be satisfactorily positioned in 5.1 format.

The performance practice of Stockhausen's *Kontakte* for piano, percussion and tape (1958-60) has likewise experienced a modification in sound projection, in this case, however, one that was prescribed by a later edition of the score. While the first edition of the score (UE 14246) calls for a setup with channels 1-4 routed to speakers placed at the left, front, right and back of the hall (again the "rhombus" setup), the second edition (Stockhausen-Verlag Work N°121/2) places the four speakers at the four corners of the hall with channel 1 at the rear left and the channel sequence proceeding clockwise⁵, thus rotating the original disposition by 45 degrees. This disposition is easier to accommodate to most spaces and will provide a homogenous sound image avoiding the strong difference between the front and the rear speaker. Nevertheless, channels 2 and 3 now correspond better to the positions of piano and percussion at the left and right side instead of channels 1 and 3 in the early disposition. Since channels 1 and 3 contain many

² Detailed discussions of these examples can be found in the online project database: <http://www.ppeam.zhdk.ch>. Contributors to the entries were all the project members mentioned above.

³ This tape had been inspected upon our visit at IPEM.

⁴ The brochure *Het Instituut voor Psychoakoestiek en Elektronische Muziek* on p. 11 lists *Szenario* as a 4-track work.

⁵ The UE edition also has instructions for using a stereo version of the tape, an option absent from the later edition.

instances of “instrumental” sounds, these in the former variant literally create more “contacts” with the instruments. Using the original speaker setup is thus seriously to be considered, taking into account the morphological and spatial relations between instrumental and adjacent electronic sounds at specific “moments”.⁶

For Harvey’s eight-channel tape piece *Mortuos plango, vivos voco* (1980), the instructions supplied with the performance material advise to place the speakers around the audience in square disposition with clockwise sequence, starting with channel 1 in the left corner. According to Bruno Bossis [4], the composer had intended for a diamond-shaped setup and a different sequence to be used (s. Figure 1):

Figure 1. Diamond-shaped speaker setup suggested for Jonathan Harvey’s *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco*.

Using this disposition in many instances produces a more consistently engulfing spatial sound than the setup provided with the performance material, with clearly discernible moments of symmetry in the respective spatial disposition for example of bell and voice sounds. As is evidenced by a sketch [5], Harvey was at one point at least considering a cube setup during the composition process. This would have positioned the 8 channels on two squares, 1 to 4 on the lower, and 5 to 8 on the upper plane. This idea was possibly abandoned at a later stage; however, it corresponds more closely to the diamond setup than to the square clockwise setup. Even though the evidence points at the diamond-shaped setup as the one reflecting the composer’s intention most accurately, performers will have to be aware of and study the different setups and their merits.

In Berio’s *Différences* for five instruments and stereo tape (1958-60) one of the main ideas for the composer was for the tape to act as an image of the instrumental part, changing between varying degrees of proximity so that “the original model of the five instruments coexists alongside its image, which is continually modified until the *different* phases of transformation create an image that is completely modified and has nothing to do with the original image.” [6] The performance score for *Différences* advises for a minimum of four speakers to be used to diffuse the tape, with speakers 2 and 3 to be placed behind the musicians to play the untransformed sound material, and speakers 1 and 4 positioned at the left and right of the stage to play the transformed sounds. In passages with transformed sounds, these can also be moved between speakers 2 and 3 and 1 and 4 to create different sound perspectives. In our performance, the stereo perspective was widened by

hanging an additional pair of speakers on the right and left side of the stage.

5. FUNDAMENTAL PERFORMANCE MODALITY ISSUES

Although Maderna in the preface to his *Musica su due dimensioni* for flute and tape (1958) points out many indeterminate aspects of the score to be handled freely in each performance and states that the flute and the tape performer should achieve a “bilateral interpretation”, recreated anew in each performance, the potential of this open form today is generally only partially realized. This is especially true for the performance of the tape, which in many cases is simply played back “as is”, even though the length of the pauses between its segments does not appear to be musically motivated, but seems to suggest that the segments are meant as material to be used freely. This is further supported by three early concert recordings,⁷ the tape parts of which were presumably prepared by Maderna himself. These recordings show that the tape material had been rearranged and recombined for each performance, in some cases been shortened or even omitted. The performances realized during the project were inspired by the high degree of interpretative freedom witnessed by these early recordings, facilitated today by the use of digital technologies. The goal was to allow for a close musical interaction between instrument and tape and for a wide variety of formal relations inherent to the idea of open form.

Sofia Gubaidulina’s *String Quartet No. 4* (1993) uses three layers of music played by the strings (two of which are to be pre-recorded) and three layers of light projections (called “colour organ” in the score). Some aspects of the realization of these projections are, however, not explained in the score. The publisher does not provide additional information. For example, the score explicitly calls for a “colour black” to be used while also directing fading in and out from or to “nothing”. Is the latter the same as the “colour black”? Are different colours in the same colour “voice” to be projected separately or should they be mixed? Should the sound projection be linked to the spatial disposition of the light projection? These questions were discussed in a written exchange with the composer. As for the relationship between sound and color projection, Gubaidulina stated that the sound projection should be independently and freely conceived [7]. For the different colours in a voice, these should be projected separately and not onto screens, but in such a way that they would colour the space, e. g. through use of theatrical fog. Finally, the composer pointed out that while fading to or from “nothing” meant merely the absence of a light source, the “colour black” had been understood as a distinct colour, playing an important role in the overall dramaturgy.

⁶ Stockhausen referred to the sections of *Kontakte* as “Momente”, s. K.-H. Stockhausen, *Texte zur elektronischen und instrumentalen Musik*, Vol. 1, Köln, pp. 189, 1963. See ppeam.zhdk.ch for a complete discussion, which also includes remarks on the synchronization issues.

⁷ Naples (June 1, 1958), Darmstadt (September 5, 1958) and Köln (1959), all performed by flutist Severino Gazzelloni.

6. RECONSTRUCTION AND RE-INTERPRETATION

In cases where the original performance environment no longer exists and/or new performance situations can be envisioned, reconstruction and re-interpretation becomes an issue.

The possibility of experiencing the originally intended multimedia work *Poème* conceived for the Philips pavilion at the Brussels World Fair of 1958 had obviously been lost with the dismantling of the pavilion itself. Kees Tazelaar's video version, which was discussed and performed during the project, is a recent attempt at more accurately representing the original conception, using the production tapes and the 35mm perfo-tape held at the Institute of Sonology, The Hague, and drawing on original sketches to recreate the spatial movement of sounds and the visual part, combining video and 5.1 surround sound [8].

Luciano Berio's tape piece *Visage* (1961) is licensed by the publisher for radio broadcasts only. Any concert performance of the piece requires special approval. If this actually reflects the composer's intention seems at least unclear, as the piece at one point apparently had been performed in a scenic setting with Cathy Berberian and a written statement by Berio on the issue merely states that the piece's "destination is not absolutely the concert hall." [9] Also, the fact that this is a stereo piece implies a conscious interest in the spatial dimension that could not have been represented in radio broadcasts, which at the time were in mono. Alvis Vidolin's version of *Visage*, which was discussed and performed during the project, draws on this original spatial conception and uses current technology to accommodate a 9+1 loudspeaker setup, placing the voice on a new third track (attained through spectral subtraction) and projecting it over a central cluster of speakers, while the stereo image is independently projected into a surround perspective.

For Ligeti's *Glissandi* (1957), no performance practice history involving the composer is known. During the project the performance team decided to develop a performance using several loudspeakers in a three-dimensional array, but maintaining a stable sound image in the centre corresponding to the original mono source. While this would not seem a very likely approach historically, the concept used in the spatialization was derived from an analytical study of the piece, thus translating, re-interpreting original features of the piece on a spatial level.

7. DISSEMINATION

The question of appropriate research output formats was particularly relevant in this practice-based project, as it aimed especially to contribute to concert performance practice. Accordingly, the two main outputs we focused on were a performance practice database and a SACD release.

7.1 Electroacoustic Performance Practice Database

The works studied are documented in the *Electroacoustic Performance Practice Database* (<http://ppeam.zhdk.ch>),

intended above all as a practical resource for performers. It unifies information relevant to the performance of specific pieces and aims to contribute to the establishment and spread of an informed electroacoustic performance culture. It currently includes works by composers Luciano Berio, Pierre Boulez, Morton Feldman, Brian Ferneyhough, Gérard Grisey, Sofia Gubaidulina, Jonathan Harvey, Klaus Huber, Mauricio Kagel, Helmut Lachenmann, Györgi Ligeti, Bruno Maderna, Steve Reich, Karlheinz Stockhausen and Edgard Varèse. The entries, reflecting the research and rehearsal processes, provide information about the historic context of works and their significance within a composer's output, a discussion of available sources, information on performance instructions (where available), reports on the performances realized during the research project, a selected bibliography and a schematic synopsis of each entry for quick reference. The database was conceived as a dynamic resource to be expanded and updated as ICST's research on electroacoustic performance practice evolves in the future. Hence, the information provided is not necessarily exhaustive. Users are encouraged to share any relevant additional information or point out any inaccuracies.

7.2 SACD publication

The double SACD "Les Espaces Electroacoustiques", published on the Austrian label "col legno" in November 2016 is also an important part of the project's output. It contains a selection of works studied during the project, which are presented in 5.1 and stereo. It includes György Ligeti's *Glissandi* and *Artikulation*, Varèse's *Poème électronique*, Luciano Berio's *Différences* and *Visage*, Bruno Maderna's *Musica su due dimensioni*, Helmut Lachenmann's *Szenario*, Jonathan Harvey's *Mortuos plango, vivos voco*, Boulez' *Dialogue de l'ombre double* and Brian Ferneyhough's *Mnémosyne*. Apart from making these works available in surround for the first time, the release presents possible performance approaches derived from the research and demonstrates the challenge of adapting them to different formats and purposes.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The exchange between musicologists and performers in this project afforded both groups specific challenges and opportunities. On the one hand, performers could profit greatly from becoming aware of source-related issues, the implications of performance traditions, historic studio practices, historic technologies and formats, etc. The musicologists on the other hand had a chance to gain first-hand insight into practical technological and performance-related issues, and to listen to the audio sources under the best possible conditions.

Of the many issues touched upon during this project, problems with respect to the available performance material and documentation for pieces have to be the most urgent ones in a practical sense. For such cases, it would be desirable for researchers, performers, archives and publishers to work together closely to ensure that the best material available and relevant information are made accessible to performers.

Notwithstanding the fact that this specific project focused mainly on historic pieces, the insights gained may contribute to the general awareness of challenges presented by a performing art highly dependent on technology. The problem of documentation, preservation and access to sources and performance material concerns composers, performers, publishers and archives alike. A follow-up project at ICST will focus on the issues presented by works involving live electronics.

9. REFERENCES

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